

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF TECHNOLOGY IN SUPPORTING MULTIPLE INTELLIGENCES FOR COLLABORATIVE AND PERSONALIZED LEARNING, INSIGHTS FROM ALBANIAN TEACHERS

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Abstract

Although the theory of multiple intelligences is widely recognized, its application remains new in Albania, with notable gaps in practice. This study aims to explore teachers' perceptions of the theory of multiple intelligences, analyze its application, and evaluate the role of technology in fostering these intelligences while promoting more collaborative and personalized learning experiences.

A mixed-methods approach was employed to identify, measure, and generalize the variables in a sample of 149 in-service teachers. Data was analyzed using SPSS, with correlation analysis revealing relationships among variables. A significant positive correlation ($r = 0.511$) indicates that as teachers use technology to stimulate multiple intelligences, students are more engaged in collaborative and personalized learning environments.

Teachers who understand multiple intelligences and effectively use technology create more engaging, collaborative, and personalized learning spaces. These findings highlight the importance of integrating technology into education to enhance learning outcomes and encourage student-centered approaches. By leveraging advances in technology, educators can support collaborative and personalized learning tailored to students' unique intelligences, fostering more effective and meaningful educational experiences.

Keywords: multiple intelligences, in-service teachers, technology tools, personalised learning approach.

INTRODUCTION

Howard Gardner's theory of multiple intelligences is well known, but the question remains how it can be applied to teaching and learning processes, particularly in today's school settings, where personalized learning seems to be a demand. Understanding the strengths and weaknesses related to the different intelligences of each student can help achieve greater success in learning. Technology can be used to facilitate learning in all areas of intelligences. Howard Gardner through a series of research [16, 19] for his theory of multiple intelligences identified differentiated types of intelligence.

Linguistic intelligence is related to the ability to use clear and effective vocabulary. Those with it usually know how to change linguistic register as needed and strive to reflect on language. Students learn best through language comprehension, which includes speaking, writing, reading, and listening [3, 27]. Students with linguistic intelligence in personalized learning or in collaboration with others can easily access a wealth of information through databases, computer networks, non-digital and digital technologies. The development of language skills can be acquired by using technology to access, share and manage information, communicate, learn, and develop intelligence. Various technological means can be used for this intelligence,

including word processors, desktop publishing tools, web-based publishing tools, speech recognition software, concept maps, story-creation software, etc., [25].

Logical-mathematical intelligence deals with deductive reasoning, schematization, and logical chains. Those who possess this intelligence are believed to have logical, problem-solving, creative, and manipulative abilities, to absorb information using mental images from different perspectives, and to appreciate a range of evaluative tasks such as measuring, calculating, and organizing [6, 7]. Students can hone their critical thinking skills using technologies that provide ways to explore mathematics and combine it with creativity. Various technologies can be used, including online calculation tools, graphing calculators and software, spreadsheets, and WebQuest, problem solving activities, multimedia authoring, programming languages, etc., [12, 29].

Visual-spatial intelligence concerns the ability to perceive shapes and objects in space. Those with it usually have a developed memory for environmental details, external features of figures, recognize three-dimensional objects based on complex mental schemas, and appear in the creation of figurative arts. Multimedia tools allow students to create reports and activities that incorporate text, drawings, animations, video, and

sound. Other technological means that may be useful here: monitors, digital cameras and camcorders, scanners, videos, presentations, graphing and diagramming tools, graphic editors, HTML editors, CAD, 3D and morphing software, digital animations, and movies, etc., [35, 36].

Students with bodily-kinesthetic intelligence have a mastery of the body that enables well-coordinated movements and creative use of the body. This intelligence includes tangible skills such as coordination, balance, power, flexibility, and speed [3, 10]. Students can choose different technologies that fit the goal of this intelligence. Creativity software, simulations requiring hand-eye coordination, assistive technology, animation, can provide new opportunities for "hands-on" learning [32].

Musical intelligence is the ability to recognize pitch and harmonic constructions, to have a strong talent for the use of musical instruments or voice modulation. Students appreciate and benefit from the infinite variety of sounds used to alert, entertain, and inform computer users. Using text-to-speech software, students hear texts read aloud with a variety of musical and original sounds. Multimedia creation tools allow them to incorporate speech, sounds and music into their projects. Online game models, music generation software, and multimedia presentations can help stimulate this intelligence [20, 11].

Interpersonal intelligence concerns the ability to understand the needs, fears, and hidden desires of others, i.e., to create favorable social situations, to promote useful social and personal patterns, and to include skills in understanding points of view other than one's own. Students with this intelligence work best in groups, and technology is a great tool for collaborative learning. Tools such as chats, forums, bulletin boards, collaborative computer software or games, peer tutoring, are particularly well suited for this intelligence [23, 24].

Intrapersonal intelligence is the awareness of one's own feelings, thoughts, concerns, that is, the ability to use this self-understanding to control impulses, one's behavior, to make plans and decisions. Technologies enable students to research and learn at their own pace. Personal choice software, interactive tutorials, online forms and surveys, real-time projects, problem solving software, digital portfolios as self-assessment tools are particularly useful in stimulating this intelligence [12, 43].

Natural intelligence deals with knowledge, identifying natural objects, classifying them in a proper order and understanding the relationships between them. Students can use technology to learn about the weather, endangered animals, plants, and distant places on Earth and beyond. Websites, dedicated science software and environmental simulations allow for experimentation. Other technological means useful for stimulating this intelligence can be file managers, semantic mapping tools, databases, life science programs, nature sound files, etc. [39, 45]

Existential (observational) intelligence concerns the ability to consciously reflect on theoretical topics, such as the nature of the universe and human

knowledge. It also concerns sophistic processes, conceptual categories that can be universally valid. Technology provides means that encourage individuals to think deeply about their own purposes. Environments, virtual communities and visits, blogs, wikis, simulations, etc., are effective means to stimulate this intelligence [8, 15].

Today's technologies can be used to create learning programs that function to promote the optimal development of any type of intelligence. These technologies stimulate intelligences and enable following processes [1, 34, 43, 9, 21]:

- Personalized learning.
- Stimulating creativity.
- Facilitating collaborative learning.
- Assessing competencies in different forms

of intelligence.

Personalized learning. Research have shown that promoting a student-centered model of learning, which is based on students' temperament and individual characteristics, is critical to their academic success [2] This model aims to focus on teaching methods to ensure a student-driven learning environment. Because each student's learning abilities are different, teachers need to incorporate in-scope strategies to help students reach their potential [1]. Several researchers [31, 2, 4] have studied the impact of multiple intelligences theory on school performance and when they think about individual traits, they think about intelligence. Technology [3, 11, 21] provides many resource tools, and suggests activities that can be used to personalize learning according to an individual's different intelligence. The following are some of them that we hold important to them:

- Initial student assessment identifies strengths and weaknesses in different areas of intelligence. These assessments can include online quizzes, tests of specific skills, and analysis of prior learning data [1]
- Personalized planning is based on the results of the initial assessment; personalized learning plans can be developed for each student. These plans include specific learning materials, activities and resources targeted to develop intelligence and reinforce those in need [1].
- Adaptive learning automatically adapts teaching materials and activities based on student performance. In this way, they receive personalized learning [2].
- Immediate and personalized feedback enables such feedback on student exercises and activities and help them understand what they are doing wrong and how to improve [42].
- Integration of adaptive learning with generative artificial intelligence for learning personalization [38].

Stimulating creativity. Technology enables the creation and delivery of variable digital content that considers different intelligences [12, 34]. For example, a learning module can be presented through text, video, pictures, simulations, or interactive games to cater to different learning styles.

Facilitating collaborative learning. Several studies claim that individuals who understand themselves

well can make decisions based on their preferred social environment [26, 23]. To achieve effective learning, teachers must consider both cognitive and social-constructive processes. As such, these processes play an important role in developing metacognitive, and non-cognitive aspects such as moral, social, and emotional [24, 44]. Technology can facilitate collaboration between individuals of different intelligences and foster a collaborative learning environment by [23, 25, 37].

- facilitating communication and sharing technology which has made communication more accessible through means such as e-mail, instant messaging, video conferencing and social media.
- accessing to information. Students of different intelligence can access large amounts of information online through search engines, educational resources, and learning platforms.
- using online learning platforms, for example, Moodle provides a virtual space where students can collaborate, share materials, and participate in discussions.
- real-time collaboration tools, for example, Google Docs and Microsoft Teams, which enable people with different abilities to work together in real time.
- Participation in global learning communities, online communities and discussion forums provide places where individuals with similar interests or shared experiences can share knowledge, experiences, and resources. Technology also helps in online professional development where space and time can be fully manipulated by learners, according to one's own financial costs [13].

Assessing proficiency in multiple forms of intelligence. Multiple intelligence theory proposes a fundamental structuring of how teachers assess students' learning progress. It is important to assess in varieties of experiences, to create assessment designs consistent with the basic philosophy of multiple intelligence theory, to assess according to differentiated types of intelligence, to assess in a wide range of possible contexts in a particular field [17, 5]. Assessment procedures should be an important part of the educational process so that each type of intelligence serves as a framework for cognitive transfer [9]. Multiple intelligences profiles can also be used for indirect assessment of other personal characteristics of students, i.e., at the metacognitive and noncognitive levels [2, 37]. Technology can be a powerful tool for assessing the competencies of different forms of intelligence. The following are some ways where technology can be used to assess diverse intelligences:

- Language comprehension tests, grammar tests and writing assessments can be administered to assess an individual's language skills.
- Through learning platforms, they can assess an individual's math and problem-solving skills using quizzes, problems, and interactive tests.
- Simulation platforms can be used to assess an individual's interpersonal and intrapersonal skills through communication and social interaction scenarios.
- Using a simulation platform, an individual's interpersonal and intrapersonal skills can be assessed

through communication and social interaction scenarios.

Regarding challenges and ethical considerations there are several challenges and critical issues involved in using technology to develop multiple intelligences [30, 14, 21]. The important points are related to validity of resources, accessibility, digital distraction, dependence on technology, overuse of technology, posing of the risks to the privacy and security of personal information.

The main purpose of this article is to analyse and to estimate Albanian teachers' perception about the impact of technology on the development and enhancement of diverse intelligences to personalized and collaborative learning. The article begins with a definition of multiple intelligences, that is, a brief description of each, followed by a list of technologies, such as: software, digital teaching tools, learning platforms, simulations, and digital games, etc., that can be used in relation to the characteristics and roles of each type of intelligence.

The theoretical framework analyzes the information gathered, and explains how technology can be used to personalize learning considering the different intelligences of students; how technology can be used to enhance creativity in different intelligences is explored; how technology facilitates collaboration among individuals of different intelligences and promotes an inclusive and collaborative learning environment is illustrated; ethical considerations related to the use of technology in multiple intelligences are considered, including issues such as privacy, security, and equitable access to resources.

The methodology used for this research involves empirical investigation such as survey, using mixed methods of quantitative and qualitative analysis.

A limitation of this study could be its exclusive focus on the teachers' point of view, without directly including the perspectives of students or other key actors in the educational context.

METHODOLOGY

Mixed method design. This study is based on an analytic literature review mainly on technology integration in teaching and learning process related to multiple intelligence, as part of personalized and collaborative to students' learning. The methodology used for this research involves empirical investigation such as survey, using mixed methods of quantitative and qualitative analysis. The survey is designed, calculated, and analyzed empirically. Some descriptive analyses, crosstabulation and correlation coefficient analyses of different items are used.

Participants. The population included a sample of in-service teachers (n=149). They teach at different levels of education and were selected on a non-probabilistic random choice sampling technique, by using the snowball technique. Participation in the study was voluntary, and ethical considerations such as confidentiality and anonymity were emphasized during the presentation. The personal information collected from each teacher was (a) gender, (b) years of work, (c) qualification, (d) the school cycle in which they work, and (e)

type of school, where anonymity was always maintained. They have an average of 18.8 years' work experience as teachers.

Research instrument and data analysis. The survey was conducted online, and teachers were informed in advance of how to complete it. The items of the survey are closed and open type. Despite general information, the items covered the main topics of the theoretical framework related to the scope of work, covering critical issues related to personalized learning, creativity, collaborative learning, assessment, challenges, and ethical challenges and considerations, associated with the use for the development of multiple intelligences. The collected data were processed according to the SPSS software, making it possible to perform statistical analysis through the results in frequency, cross-tabulation, and Spearman correlation. Cronbach's alpha reliability test was performed, and the result obtained was Cronbach's $\alpha = .738$. This value indicates an acceptable level of reliability [41]. The resulting value

of it, more than 0.6 indicate that the questionnaire used is reliable [28].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Most of the teachers are female (81.2%) and male (18.8%). Among them, 37.6% belong to high-skilled teachers, 28.2% are specialist teachers, 20.1% are qualified teachers, 7.4% are unqualified teachers, and 6.7% belong to "other" category. This result indicates that the teachers are well prepared and have a lot of work experience (65,8%). In terms of level school, 36.2% of them work in low middle schools, 20.1% in high middle schools, 30.9% in primary schools, 6.7% in other schools, and 6% in united schools. The distribution of teachers based on school type evidence that 87.2% work in public schools, and 12.8% in private schools. They spend an average of 3.96 hours per week on self-training technology. Interestingly, there is no observed relationship between training hours and work experience as teachers (Figure. 1), suggesting that technology integration is not constrained by time limitation, but rather serves as a complementary tool for their needs.

Figure. 1: Linear regression. Relationship between time spent on self-training and work experience as a teacher

To question "When considering the integration of technology in educational approaches, which three intelligences do you believe are most effectively supported?", the teachers' responses highlighted the following percentages of intelligence distribution: logical-mathematical intelligence 64.4%, spatial intelligence 54.4%, musical intelligence 47.7%, linguistic intelligence 45%, existential or observational intelligence 27.5%, naturalist intelligence 24.8%, interpersonal intelligence 20.1%, bodily-kinesthetic intelligence 11.4%, intrapersonal intelligence 4.7%. Note the notably low percentage for intrapersonal intelligence.

Regarding the question of whether teachers use special technological tools designed to stimulate a specific type of intelligence and what those tools consist of, 31.54% of respondents answered negatively while 67.78% answered positively. A good portion of the teachers who answered positively also presented specific methods they use within the technology. Most of

them, 21.8%, mention logic games, 16.6% mention music applications and 10.89% mention graphic software. Other responses are divided among videos, simulations, quizzes on various online platforms, mathematical applications, etc.

In response to the question "What do you consider to be the main ethical challenges associated with the use of technology in enhancing multiple intelligences? Please select three alternatives," they responded as follows technological dependency (80.5%), lack of equal access to technology (79.2%), privacy and data security (69.8%), Discrimination, bullying, lack of accountability (55.7%), impact on self-esteem if results are negative (14.8%). The responses indicate that technological dependency, lack of equal access to technology, and concerns about privacy and data security are perceived as the primary ethical challenges associated with using technology to enhance multiple intelligences. The issue

of unequal access to technology is particularly prominent compared to concerns about privacy and data security.

Teachers (53.4%), regardless of their teaching experience, believe that technology promotes creativity in different intelligences, especially those with more than 5 years of work experience. (Table. 1) The technological approach enables students to engage with content

through text, video, simulations, and interactive games, addressing their unique needs and enhancing their creative capacities. Learning by doing is a learning goal to train future people [34]. It is important to balance technology use with a focus on the quality and meaningfulness of creative experience.

Table. 1

Crosstabulation between “Qualification” and question “Do you believe that technology can foster creativity in different intelligences?”

		Do you believe that technology can foster creativity in different intelligences?					Total	
		No, I do not believe	Yes, technology has limited impact	I am unsure about that	Yes, I believe, technology promote creativity	Yes, I believe, technology has an important role		
Qualification	Qualified Teacher	Count	1	1	2	20	6	30
		% of Total	0.7%	0.7%	1.3%	13.4%	4.0%	20.1%
	Specialist teacher	Count	3	4	5	23	7	42
		% of Total	2.0%	2.7%	3.4%	15.4%	4.7%	28.2%
	Highly skilled Teacher	Count	2	10	3	37	4	56
		% of Total	1.3%	6.7%	2.0%	24.8%	2.7%	37.6%
	Unclassified Teacher	Count	0	4	0	5	2	11
		% of Total	0.0%	2.7%	0.0%	3.4%	1.3%	7.4%
Other	Count	0	1	1	4	4	10	
	% of Total	0.0%	0.7%	0.7%	2.7%	2.7%	6.7%	
Total	Count	6	20	11	89	23	149	
	% of Total	4.0%	13.4%	7.4%	59.7%	15.4%	100.0%	

In response to the question about having collaborative learning experiences involving students with different intelligences, 51% of teachers gave positive answers. Overall, teachers seem to consider group work and collaboration as experiences of integrating students with different intelligences. It seems that the concept of multiple intelligences is merged and recognized with that of teamwork and cooperation. Collaboration generates diverse perspectives, participatory learning, synergies, and viable solutions [33, 43]. The case of a response (respondent 76) mentions students collaborating to stage a theatrical piece, where someone handles the musical column, someone the scenography, someone the costumes and someone else deals with acoustics, implies an organization based on intelligences. Teachers create value by helping students acquire knowledge and skills and supporting institutions personally and collaboratively [18].

Project work seems to be the instructional activity that most teachers consider collaborative learning based on intelligence. Their responses mention: project-based learning (respondents 7, 18, 49); interdisciplinary projects (respondents 23, 52, 145); research project (respondent 108); comprehensive technology and arts-focused projects. On the other hand, there are responses that focus on the different talents or creative abilities of individual students, rather than on group – based cooperative activities, which teachers organize and involve students with certain intelligences. These

responses mention students who engage in coding (respondents 90, 105); robot programming (respondent 80); software use (respondent 36); platforms like "GeoGebra" or "PhET" (respondent 80) etc. Education allows students to be creative and critically examine situations, enabling them to improve skills and competencies, preparing them for future jobs in today's fast-growing competitive and challenging environment

Among the types of intelligences developed during the learning process, teachers mostly mention visual-spatial intelligence, highlighting students' engagement in work with sketches, drawings, but also linguistic, logical-mathematical intelligence, musical intelligence, etc.

In response to the question, “What would you suggest to educators or technology designers to improve the integration of technology in education and enhance the educational approach based on multiple intelligences? Please choose the 3 most important for you”, they answered by: providing training for teachers for technological proficiency (69.8%), creating applications and platforms that allow a personalized experience for students (59.1%), equal access to technological resources and high-speed internet (51%), creating multimedia content (28.2%), encouraging collaboration and idea exchange (30.9%), integrating applications to stimulate multiple intelligences (36.9%). The most critical suggestion is providing technological pro-

iciency training for teachers, underscoring the importance of equipping teachers with the necessary skills to effectively use technology in the classroom. Respondents emphasize the need for creating applications and platforms that offer personalized learning experiences for students, indicating a strong desire for technology that adapts to individual learning needs. Identifying the relevance of personality traits is important because it can inform the skills, knowledge, and methods that teachers and curriculum creators should focus on when designing and implementing educational processes [2, 34].

Table 2 is a correlation matrix which shows the correlation coefficients between different variables, whether they are related, the strength and direction of this relation. There are analyzed those variables or questions which present a significant relation, with high reliability level and statistically significant. The p-value is found to be $p = 0.000$, indicating that this relationship is statistically significant with a high level of reliability (99%, statistical error only 1%). The correlated variables are:

question (Q_A) "Are you aware of the concept of "Multiple Intelligences" as formulated by H. Gardner?",

question (Q_B) "Have you ever used any specific technological tools designed to stimulate a particular intelligence (e.g., musical applications, graphic software, logic games, etc.)?",

question (Q_C) "Have you had experiences in teaching that have taken into account the different intelligences and abilities of students?",

question (Q_D) "Do you believe that technology can foster creativity in different intelligences?",

question (Q_E) "Have you had collaborative learning experiences with students focusing on multiple intelligences?",

question (Q_F) "How has technology influenced the way you assess learning based on different intelligences?",

question (Q_G) "Have you ever had the opportunity to participate in training courses or seminars focused on using technology to develop multiple intelligences?".

Table 2.

Correlation matrix of Spearman's rho correlation coefficients between different variables.

		Q_A	Q_B	Q_C	Q_D	Q_E	Q_F	Q_G
Spearman's rho	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.378**	.360**	.209*	.332**	.231**	.152
	Q_A Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000	.000	.011	.000	.005	.064
	N	149	149	149	149	149	149	149
	Correlation Coefficient	.378**	1.000	.401**	.286**	.511**	.183*	.215**
	Q_B Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	.000	.000	.000	.026	.008
	N	149	149	149	149	149	149	149
	Correlation Coefficient	.360**	.401**	1.000	.359**	.592**	.212**	.268**
	Q_C Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.	.000	.000	.010	.001
	N	149	149	149	149	149	149	149
	Correlation Coefficient	.209*	.286**	.359**	1.000	.331**	.476**	.023
	Q_D Sig. (2-tailed)	.011	.000	.000	.	.000	.000	.778
	N	149	149	149	149	149	149	149
	Correlation Coefficient	.332**	.511**	.592**	.331**	1.000	.243**	.385**
	Q_E Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.	.003	.000
	N	149	149	149	149	149	149	149
	Correlation Coefficient	.231**	.183*	.212**	.476**	.243**	1.000	.056
	Q_F Sig. (2-tailed)	.005	.026	.010	.000	.003	.	.498
	N	149	149	149	149	149	149	149
	Correlation Coefficient	.152	.215**	.268**	.023	.385**	.056	1.000
	Q_G Sig. (2-tailed)	.064	.008	.001	.778	.000	.498	.
	N	149	149	149	149	149	149	149

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

a) *The relationship between awareness of the concept of "Multiple Intelligences" as formulated by H. Gardner to the usage of specific technological tools designed to stimulate a particular intelligence (e.g., musical applications, graphic software, logic games, etc.)?* H₀: There is no relationship between the level of awareness of the concept of "Multiple Intelligences" as formulated by H. Gardner to the level of the usage of

specific technological tools designed to stimulate a particular intelligence (e.g., musical applications, graphic software, logic games, etc.). H_a: There is a relationship between level of awareness of Howard Gardner's "Multiple Intelligences" theory and the use of technological tools designed to stimulate multiple intelligences.

The correlation coefficient is calculated as $r = 0.378$. As the coefficient value is not very close to +1, it indicates a *weak correlation* between the variables.

The positive sign of the coefficient suggests that the direction of the relation is the same: as awareness of the concept of "Multiple Intelligences" increases, so does the usage of specific technological tools to stimulate intelligences, and vice versa.

b) *The relationship between awareness of the concept of "Multiple Intelligences" as formulated by H. Gardner to the experiences in teaching that have considered the different intelligences and abilities of students.* H₀: There is no relationship between the level of awareness of the concept of "Multiple Intelligences" as formulated by H. Gardner to the experiences in teaching that have considered the different intelligences and abilities of students. H_a: There is a relationship between awareness of Howard Gardner's "Multiple Intelligences" theory and teaching experiences that consider students' diverse intelligences and abilities.

The correlation coefficient is computed as $r = 0.360$. Since the coefficient value is not very close to +1, it signifies a *weak correlation* between the variables. The positive sign of the coefficient implies that the direction of the relation is consistent: as awareness of the concept of "Multiple Intelligences" increases, so does the consideration of different intelligences and abilities of teachers in teaching practices and vice versa.

c) *The relationship between usage of any specific technological tools designed to stimulate a particular intelligence (e.g., musical applications, graphic software, logic games, etc.) to the experiences in teaching that have considered the different intelligences and abilities of students.* H₀: There is no relationship between the usage of the specific technological tools designed to stimulate a particular intelligence (e.g., musical applications, graphic software, logic games, etc.) to the experiences in teaching that have considered the different intelligences and abilities of students. H_a: There is a relationship between the use of technological tools for multiple intelligences and teaching experiences that consider students' diverse abilities. In this case computed r is 0.401. Since the coefficient value is not very close to +1, it indicates an *average correlation* between the variables. The positive sign of the coefficient means that as the usage of the specific technological tools designed to stimulate a particular intelligence (e.g., musical applications, graphic software, logic games, etc.) increases, so does the consideration of different intelligences and abilities of teachers in teaching practices and vice versa.

d) *The relationship between the usage of specific technological tools designed to stimulate a particular intelligence (e.g., musical applications, graphic software, logic games, etc.) to the collaborative learning experiences with students focusing on multiple intelligences.* H₀: There is no relationship between the usage of specific technological tools designed to stimulate a

particular intelligence to the level of the collaborative learning experience with students focusing on multiple intelligence. H_a: there are links between what teachers prefer to use regarding the specific technological tool and the students' collaborative learning focusing on multiple intelligences.

The computed correlation coefficient ($r = 0.511$) highlights a *strong correlation* between these variables. The direction of the relationship is positive. The finding evidence is that the more teachers use technological tools that stimulate multiple intelligences, the more students experience and are encouraged in such collaborative environments that focus on multiple intelligences. Technological advances in the era of digitalization are viewed as a medium of making personalized learning possible [40].

e) *The relationship between the experiences in teaching that have considered the different intelligences and abilities of students to the collaborative learning experiences with students focusing on multiple intelligences.* H₀: There are no relationship between experiences in teaching that have considered the different intelligences and abilities of students to the level of the collaborative learning experience with students focusing on multiple intelligence. H_a: the experiences in teaching that have considered the different intelligences and abilities of students to the collaborative learning experiences with students focusing on multiple intelligences.

In this case, the computed correlation coefficient ($r = 0.592$) evidences a *strong correlation* between questions. The direction of the relation is positive. Teachers value both aspects, so they increase the experiences in teaching that consider the different intelligences and abilities of the students and increase the level of collaborative learning experiences with the students, focusing on multiple intelligences.

The study found the same positive relationship between the question: "Do you believe that technology can foster creativity in different intelligences?" and the question "How has technology influenced the way you assess learning based on different intelligences?" with an *average correlation* ($r = 0.476$) and statistical significance. This demonstrates that teachers believe the use of technology can foster creativity in different intelligences and influence assessment methods by considering different multiple intelligences.

Meanwhile, the study found that the more work experience teachers, the more they expressed a desire for availability at levels of sometimes available, very available, and always available (Table 3). Thus, it is observed that teachers express interest in different pedagogical experiences and approaches for the benefit of the teaching and learning process.

Table 3.

Crosstabulation between qualification and the availability of the teachers to participate in training session on the topic of multiple intelligences?

			The availability of the teachers to be trained on multiple intelligences?					Total
			not available	a little available	sometimes available	very available	always available	
Qualification	Qualified (20%)	Teacher Count	0	5	3	9	13	30
		% of Total	0.0%	3.4%	2.0%	6.0%	8.7%	20.1%
	Specialist (28%)	Teacher Count	1	2	7	17	15	42
		% of Total	0.7%	1.3%	4.7%	11.4%	10.1%	28.2%
	Highly skilled (37.6%)	Teacher Count	1	4	20	20	11	56
		% of Total	0.7%	2.7%	13.4%	13.4%	7.4%	37.6%
	Unclassified (7.4%)	Teacher Count	0	1	2	6	2	11
		% of Total	0.0%	0.7%	1.3%	4.0%	1.3%	7.4%
	Other	Count	0	0	2	4	4	10
		% of Total	0.0%	0.0%	1.3%	2.7%	2.7%	6.7%
Total		Count	2	12	34	56	45	149
		% of Total	1.3%	8.1%	22.8%	37.6%	30.2%	100.0%

Schools and educational institutions should implement professional development training that train teachers about the concept of multiple intelligences and educate them on using specific technological tools. These training can help teachers integrate technological tools into their teaching practices, thereby enhancing student engagement and learning outcomes

CONCLUSIONS

While the theory of multiple intelligences is widely accepted globally, a different situation is presented in Albania. The conclusions of this study indicate that:

- More than half of the teachers believe that logical-mathematical and visual-spatial intelligences are better supported by technology in educational approaches. More than 70% of teachers evidence technology dependence, lack of equal access to technology, privacy and data security as ethical challenges related to the use of technology in the stimulation of multiple intelligences. To improve the integration of technology in education and strengthen the educational approach based on multiple intelligences, teachers suggest prioritizing the provision of training for technological competence and the creation of applications and platforms that enable a personalized experience for students. At the same time, the integration of applications for the stimulation of multiple intelligences and the implementation of assessments of student progress based on these intelligences seem to be less of a priority.

- In a few cases, teachers show that they take the different types of intelligence into account when organizing group work. A weak but statistically significant positive correlation ($r = 0.360$) exists, suggesting that greater awareness of multiple intelligences is associated with more teaching practices that consider students' different intelligences and abilities. A strong positive correlation ($r = 0.592$) indicates that teachers who incorporate different intelligences and abilities into their teaching also tend to foster collaborative learning experiences focused on multiple intelligences. Correlation analysis of the study demonstrates that increasing

awareness and use of tools supporting multiple intelligences correlates with enhanced teaching practices and collaborative learning environments, underscoring the value of integrating technology and diverse intelligence-focused approaches in education.

The results of this study will help teachers promote greater integration of the theory of multiple intelligences in Albanian education and help improve teaching practice to foster more effective and personalized learning. Awareness of multiple intelligences significantly influences teaching practices. Teachers who understand and apply Gardner's theory in their classrooms are more likely to consider the diverse intelligences and abilities of their students. This insight highlights the necessity for professional development and training programs that focus on multiple intelligences to improve teaching effectiveness and personalized student engagement.

Educational policymakers, school administrators and teachers should invest in and provide access to a variety of technological tools that cater to different intelligences.

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